

**ASSESSING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF QUALITY ASSURANCE
IN BUSINESS EDUCATION PROGRAMME SUSTAINABILITY**

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Abstract: This study examined quality assurance as a tool for business education programme sustainability in Rivers state university. Three objectives, three research questions and three null hypotheses formulated guided the study. The study adopted descriptive survey research design. The population of the study consisted of thirty (30) lecturers in business Education Department in Rivers state university. Due to the manageable size of the population, there was no sample and sampling technique adopted. The instrument for data collection was a selfstructured questionnaire, structured on a four-point rating scale. The instrument was validated by three experts, two from the Department of business education and another expert in measurement and evaluation, all in faculty of education. Out of 30 copies of questionnaire administered, 23 copies were retrieved, representing 77 percent retrieval. The reliability of the instrument was determined using Pearson Product Moment correlation coefficient. The coefficient obtained was 0.82 which showed that the respondents acknowledged that to high extent, quality assurance can be used to sustain business education programme through effective monitoring, provision of intellectual learning materials and sustain disciplinary measures by business education lecturers in rivers state university. Based on the findings of the study it was recommended among others that more emphasis should be placed on the quality of personnel in business education programme and more disciplinary measures should be adopted by those in-charge of quality assurance on any individual that defaults.

Keywords: Quality Assurance, Business Education Programme, Sustainability

Introduction

The role of education towards the development of any nation cannot be over emphasized. Education is one of the most important inputs for the well-being of any society. It is a powerful instrument of social progress without which neither an individual nor a nation can attain the growth that is necessary for development. Education whether in the form of formal, informal or non-formal mode is very important and has direct bearing with career developments on individuals. Education in its formal form is a determining factor in the realization of career aspirations. Education whether in the form of formal, informal or non-formal modes is very important and has direct bearing with career development on individuals. Education is a significant agent of socialization where individuals acquire various aptitudes, knowledge, and skills, which eventually influence their career aspiration.

Elobuiké in Ololube (2013) submitted that education means many things to many people and different things to different people. To pupils, students (whether in primary, secondary or at the tertiary level), it could be seen as a means of acquiring the necessary qualifications for job, a way of escaping lowly social life or a way of realizing their life aspirations. Business education is a branch of education that involves teaching the skills and operations of the business industry (Gordon & Bursuc, 2018). This field of education occurs at multiple levels, including secondary and higher education institutes. Education in business has many forms, mainly occurring within a classroom of a school. Internships are also another way to receive this type of education. A business education has many components, as there are many different areas of the business industry as a whole. An education in business varies greatly in its curriculum and popularity around the world. Career development is often an integral part of an education in business. Education and collaboration from business and management faculties contributing to sustainable development, which is understood as advancing 'the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. Quality assurance is introduced into education to ensure that a school develops and performs in line with the laid down procedure of education. These standards can be assessed both internally and externally to ensure that every school follows quality assurance guidelines. Schools are usually assessed on education and training. These assessments can involve school self-evaluation, external evaluation, and evaluation of teachers, school leaders and student assessment to make sure they are reaching their targets. These can include inspectors arriving in school and teacher appraisals. It involves the systematic review of educational programme and processes to maintain and improve their quality, equity and efficiency. While the design of quality assurance mechanisms (tools, processes and actors) varies across national contexts, with the aim of improving teaching and learning which is the ultimate goal to support the best outcomes for learners (Askling, 2014). Quality assurance approaches include mechanisms to monitor academic activities, provide intellectual learning materials and ensure judicious utilization of financial resources as a process of maintaining, and improving the quality of a higher education system, institutions, or programme. As a regulatory mechanism, quality assurance focuses on both accountability and improvement, providing information and judgments through an agreed upon and consistent process and well-established criteria. These mechanisms have different but complementary purposes geared towards sustaining the education system. Higher education has a unique opportunity to provide learning for the future and help the world address the rapidly unfolding social, cultural, economic and environmental sustainability challenges of the 21st century. However, to fulfill this role at the regional, national and international levels, higher education institutions themselves have to undergo critical transformation towards sustainable development in their philosophy and practices and put in place the quality assurance systems to ensure that this transformation is consistently implemented and effective. Therefore, sustainability is a societal goal with three dimensions or pillars such as; the environmental, economic and social dimension. The social dimension concept includes how to guide decisions at the global, national and at institutional level (Purvis, Mao & Robinson, 2019).

Quality Assurance as a Tool for Sustainability in Education

Here the different approaches to quality that qualifies quality assurance as a tool for sustainability is described. Quality assurance agencies can adopt one or more of these according to different educational systems and traditions (Woodhouse, 2018). The three main approaches to quality are accreditation, assessment and audit. Accreditation and evaluation (which includes assessment and audit) differ in their perspectives. Both accreditation and assessment monitor the quality of teaching and learning, while audit focuses on internal procedures adopted by a HEI in order to achieve its objectives.

1. Accreditation

Accreditation is an evaluation of whether an institution or gaining accreditation may have implications for the HEI itself (e.g. permission to operate) and/or its students (e.g. eligibility for grants) (Woodhouse, 2018). The focus of accreditation is comprehensive, examining the mission, resources, and procedures of a HEI or programme (Dill, 2012). The output of an accreditation is a yes/no decision, though graduations are also possible (Woodhouse, 2018). Accreditation is a widely used method in quality assurance in OECD countries. In the United States accreditation of both programme and institutions is the main quality assurance method (Eaton, 2004). Accreditation of programme is used on a regular basis by about half of the European quality assurance agencies. This method is frequently used in German-speaking countries, in the associated countries, the Dutch and also Nordic and southern agencies. By Accreditation of institutions is done on a regular basis by 22% of the agencies in Europe, e.g. by German, Austrian agencies and some in the associated countries. Accreditation procedures can also focus on QAAs; for instance, United State of America accrediting organizations also undergo a periodic external review based on specific standards; this process is known as ‘recognition’ (Eaton, 2004).

2. Assessment

Assessment is an evaluation that makes graded judgments about quality, in this respect it goes beyond accreditation that makes a binary judgment (Dill, 2012). Assessment asks “how good are your outputs?” The output of an assessment is a quantitative evaluation, a grade (whether numeric, literal or descriptive) (Woodhouse, 2018). Programme and institutional assessments are widely used by European QAAs. Programme assessment is one of the most frequently used methods. It is done on a regular basis by 53% of the European agencies, mainly in the Nordic, Dutch or English-speaking countries. Focusing on programmes is particularly frequent in the non-university sector. Institutional assessment is less widespread; 22% of the European agencies are using it regularly (ENQA, 2003).

3. Audit

A quality audit checks the extent to which the institution is achieving its own explicit or implicit objectives (Woodhouse, 2018). As cited in Woodhouse (2018) “ISO (Duran 2015) defines quality audit as a three-part process, checking 1) the suitability of the planned quality procedures in relation to the stated objectives; 2) the conformity of the actual quality activities with the plans; and 3) the effectiveness of the activities in achieving the stated objectives”. Audit asks ‘are your processes effective?’ The output is a description of the extent to which the claim of the HEI are correct (Woodhouse, 2018). Academic audits are carried out at the institution level. However, unlike accreditation or assessment, audits do not aim at making a comprehensively review a HEI’s or programme’s resources and activities, nor do they directly evaluate the quality of teaching or learning. Rather audits focus on those processes implemented by HEIs in order to assure and improve the quality teaching and learning (Dill, 2012). The identity of the relevant stakeholders in higher education and how their interests may be utilized in the context of quality assurance is subject to discussion in the literature. The first question is whether stakeholders should be actively involved in quality assurance processes or whether the reviews should involve only quality assurance agencies and academics. Also, if stakeholders should have an active role, the question is what organizational implications this could have within quality assurance systems (Thune, 2017).

Sustainability of Business Education Programme through Effective monitoring

To monitor is to keep an eye on someone or something, Monitoring is used to assess the performance of projects, institutions and programme set up by governments, international organizations and NGOs. Its goal is to improve current and future management of outputs, outcomes and impact. Monitoring is a continuous assessment of

programme based on early detailed information on the progress or delay of the ongoing assessed activities. An evaluation is an examination concerning the relevance, effectiveness, efficiency and impact of activities in the light of specified objectives. Monitoring allows results, processes and experiences to be documented and used as a basis to steer decision-making and learning processes.

What to monitor

Level in

Objective Hierarchy	What to Monitor and Evaluate
Activities	Have planned activities been completed on time and within budget? What unplanned activities have been completed?
Outputs	What direct tangible products or services has the project delivered as a result of activities?
Outcome	What changes have occurred as a result of the outputs and to what extent are these likely to contribute towards the project propose and desired impact? To what extant has the project contributed towards its longer terms goals? Why or why not?
Impact	What unanticipated positive or negative Consequences did the project have? Why did they arise?

Monitoring and Evaluation

M&E is an embedded concept and constitutive part of every project or programme design (“Must be”). M&E is not an imposed control instrument by the donor or an optional accessory (“nice to have”) of any project or programme. M&E is ideally understood as dialogue on development and its progress between all stakeholders.

In general, monitoring is integral to evaluation. During an evaluation, information from previous monitoring processes is used to understand the ways in which the project or programme developed and stimulated change. Monitoring focuses on the measurement of the following aspects of an intervention:

1. On quantity and quality of the implemented activities (outputs: What do we do? How do we manage our activities?) On processes inherent to a project or programme (outcomes: What were the effects/changes that occurred as a result of your intervention?)
2. On processes external to an intervention (impact: Which broader, long-term effects were triggered by the implemented activities in combination with other environmental factors?)

The evaluation process is an analysis or interpretation of the collected data which delves deeper into the relationships between the results of the project/programme, the effects produced by the project/programme and the overall impact of the project/programme. There are three categories of monitoring:

Business process monitoring

Business process monitoring is the holy grail of systems management. All large vendors present their monitoring solution as a business process monitoring tool. Business process monitors tell us not only whether we can order goods, but also if they are being delivered to our customers. Such monitors keep track of long-running transactions and are happy to report on the proper operation of fax machines and the progress of delivery vans. Business process monitoring answers the questions of whether the business is performing well. The IT systems supporting that business are only a piece in the puzzle to answer that question.

Functional Monitoring

Functional monitoring looks at the functionality offered by a single application or by a distributed system. The aim of functional monitoring is to assess the performance and availability of use-case or set of use-cases on a

system. Functional monitoring is usually performed by employing robots to execute scripted operations on a system. Robot-based monitoring is excellent for management reports on the quality of service that the users of a system experience. Functional monitoring answers the question whether there is a problem in the distributed system or not. It says something about the performance and availability of the system, but does not help to answer that question of how to solve any problems we may find. Rather it tells us something about the impact on the users of the system, if there is a problem.

Technical Monitoring

Technical monitoring concerns itself with the health of individual pieces of equipment or software. It focuses on the function of the object under review, rather than the role that such an object plays in the system that it is part of. It may be just my skewed viewpoint, but I find that technical monitoring is by far the largest category of the three. Most tools monitoring tools were designed to perform functions in this category of monitoring. Many system operators make the mistake of thinking that technical monitoring also answers the question whether there is a problem in their system or not. It is an understandable mistake, because in many cases when there is a problem, it also shows up in the technical monitors. In some cases, however, it does not. And this is when miscommunication is likely to occur.

Sustainability of business education programme through effective Provision of Intellectual learning Material

Learning materials means any course materials or other academic materials developed, created, or used by faculty, students, or administration in connection with the facilitation or evaluation of student learning outcomes. Examples may include but are not limited to entire courses, course lecture or presentation materials, syllabus, study guides, exams, instructional materials, manuscripts, designs, any other academic-related materials utilized in connection with a course, and any derivative works or revisions thereto. The term teaching and learning materials comprise all the materials and physical means an instructor might use to implement instruction and facilitate student's achievement of instructional objectives (Ocloo, 2013). Effective teaching and learning materials may aid a student in concertizing a learning experience so as to make learning more exciting, interesting and interactive. Teaching and learning materials are materials in various forms ranging from pictures, realia, objects, models, specimens, printed materials like textbooks, workbooks, computers which could be used to influence the participation and understanding of students in learning (Ocloo, 2013). Teaching and learning materials are categorized based on a continuum and classified as lowtech, medium tech or high tech based on the level of sophistication in features, cost, level support needed to use (Chambers & Berlach, 2015). Chamber and Berlach (2015) describe low and medium-tech devices as requiring only basic instruction or and not overly complicated to operate. Low tech devices are often not electronic, simple to make and acquire such as communication boards, visual schedules, highlighter, word rings. Medium tech devices are reasonably complicated such as talking calculators, visual timers, tablets and iPad applications. Lastly, high tech devices are most complex and often specialized to accommodate a specific function and requires more training, which can include: software (Inspiration mapping), augmentative communication devices, Smart-boards.

Quality Discipline as Quality Assurance Measure in Business Education Programme

Discipline is action or inaction that is regulated to be in accordance (or to achieve accord) with a particular system of governance. Discipline is commonly applied to regulating human and animal behavior to its society or environment it belongs. In the academic and professional words a discipline is a specific branch of knowledge, learning, or practice. Discipline can be a set of expectations that are required by any governing entity including the self, groups, classes, fields, industries, or societies (Simon, 2021). Every organization, private or public, has

a set of standards and policies to be followed by members. Non-compliance will require management to enforce corrective actions. There are several types of disciplinary measures based on the gravity or seriousness of the problem. The following will help you determine the type of sanctions that may be appropriate.

Verbal Warning

For less severe misconduct, this avenue will allow human resources supervisor/manager or company representative to speak to the employee and discuss concerns or infractions without affecting their personnel record. It should outline how the employee is misbehaving and what the individual should do to improve, thereby prevent future occurrences. Management should highlight the consequences if the employee fails to do so.

Written Reprimand

This disciplinary action will serve as a precedent for future reprimands. It defines the act of misconduct, the corrective action required from the employee and repercussions if the violation is repeated. The employee should be verbally notified before adjoining the letter to the file.

Suspension

The company will suspend the employee on a temporary basis. This type of action is usually due to repeated misconduct – or because the problem requires further investigation (preventive suspension), and the presence of the employee will affect the process. Typically, this suspension will be without pay. But if the results prove that the employee is innocent, the company will be required to compensate for the lost hours/days. When suspending an employee, the company should initially submit a notification to the individual, letting the person know the reason and the actions that will be undertaken.

Financial Penalty

This type of measure is rarely used. It serves as an alternative when the employee cannot be suspended for business-related purposes (for example, if the company is restructuring, dealing with unlawful withdrawal of service, or if an individual is working overseas and cannot be replaced during the suspension period). **Demotion** Diminishing an employee's role is one of the most drastic disciplinary actions a company can take for grave misconduct or low productivity. It's usually used when an employee is incapable of handling their position or due to repeated misconduct or poor performance.

Termination

Before terminating an employee, the company must be completely sure that it went through due process and any relevant legal proceedings. A dismissal may occur when an employee doesn't correct their behaviour despite constant warnings and reminders (verbally and in writing). The employer can immediately terminate an individual if they commit a serious act of misconduct, such as stealing, harassment, or breach of contract. The company's code of conduct establishes what the consequences for specific misconduct are. Bear in mind that dismissing an employee without proper justification will have legal implications and can severely damage the company's image and finances. Therefore, it pays to carefully consider what kind of action you should take to ensure that you can sustain the termination.

Business Education Programme

Business education is a branch of education that involves teaching the skills and operations of the business industry. This field of education occurs at multiple levels, including secondary and higher education institutes (Alvarez 2015). Education in business has many forms, mainly occurring within a classroom of a school. Internships are also another way to receive this type of education. A business education has many components, as there are many different areas of the business industry as a whole. An education in business varies greatly in its

curriculum and popularity around the world. Career development is often an integral part of an education in business (Florian, 2018).

Statement of the Problem

Most higher education systems around the world have put in place a range of quality assurance, auditing and accreditation systems over the past three decades. There has been a general shift from looking at simple quality control systems to building internal capability for continuous quality assessment and improvement. Quality assurance is established and saddled with the responsibility to help maintain schools and improve the efficiency, leadership and students' progress by self and external assessments. Quality control practices in educational system is based essentially on school inspection, monitoring and control for obtaining data on policy implementation and for strategic planning and aid public accountability. Quality assurance in this context is a programme for the systematic monitoring and evaluation of the various aspects of a project, service, or facility to ensure that standards of quality are being met. Quality assurance as the preventing of quality problems through planned and systematic activities will include the establishment of a good quality management system and the assessment of its adequacy, the audit of the operation of the system, and the review of the system itself. It is one of the most critical tasks facing every nation's educational institutions, so that the societal demands for improved education service delivery would achieve the best learning outcomes that enhance the quality of life of the citizenry.

Yet, there is still poor monitoring of academic activities, inadequate provision of learning materials, and poor utilization of financial resources as well as noise pollution from individual generator among others in business education department. It is as a result of this scenario that prompted this research work.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to examine the extent to which quality assurance has been used as a tool for business education programme sustainability in Rivers state University. Specifically, the study seeks to:

1. Determine how quality assurances can be used to sustain business education programme through effective monitoring in Rivers State University.
2. Determine how quality assurance can be used to sustain business education programme through effective provision of intellectual learning materials in Rivers State University.
3. Examine how quality assurance can be used to sustain disciplinary measure among business education lecturers in Rivers State University.

Research Questions

The following research questions were formulated to guide this study

1. To what extent can quality assurance be used to sustain business education programme through effective monitoring in Rivers State University?
2. To what extent has quality assurance been used to sustain business education programme through effective provision of intellectual learning materials in Rivers State University?
3. How can quality assurance be used to sustain disciplinary measure among business education lecturers in Rivers State University?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses was tested for this study at 0.05 level of significance

1. There is no significant difference in the mean response of male and female lecturers on the use of quality assurance to sustain business education programme through effective monitoring in Rivers State University.

2. There is no significant difference in the mean response of male and female lecturers on the use of quality assurance to sustain business education programme through effective provision of intellectual learning materials in Rivers State University.

3. There is no significant difference in mean response of male and female lecturers on the use of quality assurance to sustain disciplinary measure among business education lecturers in Rivers State University.

Methods

The study adopted descriptive survey research design and was carried out in the Department of Business Education, Faculty of Education, Rivers State University. Three objectives, three research questions and three null hypotheses formulated guided the study. The population of the study consisted of thirty (30) lecturers in business Education Department in Rivers state university. Due to the manageable size of the population, there was no sample and sampling technique adopted. The instrument for data collection was a self-structured questionnaire, structured on a four-point rating scale. The instrument was validated by three experts, two from the Department of business education and another expert in measurement and evaluation, all in faculty of education and a reliability test using Cronbach Alpha method yielded an index of 0.87. The instrument for data collection was a self-developed questionnaire titled “Quality Assurance as a tool for Business Education Programme Sustainability” (QABEPS). The questionnaire was divided into two parts: Part A was concerned with the demographic information of respondents, while part B was the questionnaire proper. The questionnaire was coded using a 4-point scale of Very High Extent(VHE), High Extent(HE), Low Extent(LE), Very Low Extent(VLE). Thus, coded as: VHE - 4 points, HE - 3points, LE -2points, and VLE -1point. . Out of 30 copies of questionnaire administered, 23 copies were retrieved, representing 77 percent. The research questions was analyzed using mean and standard deviation. A decision rule was taken on a criterion mean value of 2.50. Above 2.50 was accepted and while below 2.50 was rejected. While the hypotheses was tested using t-test at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1: To what extent can quality assurance be used to sustain business education programme through effective monitoring in Rivers State University?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation on the Extent Quality Assurance can be used to sustain Business Education Programme through Effective Monitoring

S/N	Items	Female Lecturers (11)		Male Lecturers (12)		
	SD	Remark	SD	Remark		
		All lecturers are monitored by quality assurance personnel.	3.09	0.69	High Extent	2.75 0.72 High Extent
2		Quality assurance only monitors academic activities of lecturers.	2.18	1.02	Low Extent	2.00 1.15 Low Extent
3		Quality assurance monitors both lecturing and extracurricular activities of lecturers.	2.00	0.95	Low Extent	1.83 0.86 Very low Extent

4	Lecturers operate based on quality assurance guideline.	3.09	1.19	High Extent	2.25	1.00	Low Extent
5	Quality assurance accredit lecturers based on their input.	2.55	1.62	High Extent	2.42	1.11	Low Extent
Total Mean/SD		12.91	5.47		11.25	4.84	
Grand Mean/SD		2.58	1.09		2.25	0.97	

Source Field Survey, 2024

The analysis in table 1 indicates that; quality assurance sustains Business Education Programme by monitoring the quality of the personnel, providing guideline and accredit lecturers based on their input in the programme

Research Question 2: To what extent has quality assurance been used to sustain Business Education Programme through effective provision of intellectual learning materials in Rivers State University?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation on the Extent Quality Assurance can be used to sustain Business Education Programme through effective provision of intellectual Learning Materials.

S/N	Items	Female Lecturers (11) SD Remark	Male Lecturers (12) SD Remark				
	Business Education studio is regularly inspected by quality assurance personnel	2.09	0.98	Low Extent	1.83	0.90	Low Extent
2	Quality assurance provides learning materials for both lecturers and students.	2.00	1.13	Low Extent	1.75	1.00	Low Extent
3	Quality assurance unit provides elibrary for lecturers/students research.	1.73	0.96	Low Extent	1.67	0.94	Low Extent
4	Quality assurance unit ensures that all business education students pass through SIWES training.	3.00	0.74	High Extent	2.83	0.90	High Extent
5	Quality assurance unit organizes annual workshop training for lecturers.	3.00	0.85	High Extent	2.58	1.04	High Extent
Total Mean / SD		11.82	4.57		10.66	4.78	
Grand Mean /SD		2.36	0.91		2.13	0.96	

Source Field Survey, 2024

The analysis in table 2 shows that only two mean responses are up to the 2.50 acceptance region while others are

below 2.50 acceptance region. This implies that to a high extent, Quality assurance unit ensures that all Business Education Students pass through SIWES training and it organizes annual workshop training for lecturers.

However, the analysis also shows that to a low extent, Quality assurance unit does not equip Business Education studio and neither does it provide learning materials for students and lecturers

Research Question 3: How can Quality assurance be used to maintain disciplinary measure among Business Education Lecturers in Rivers State University?

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation on How Quality Assurance can be used to maintain Disciplinary Measure among Business Education Lecturers

S/N	Items	Female Lecturers (11) SD	Remark	Male Lecturers (12) SD	Remark				
1	All lecturers are subject to quality assurance order.	2.73	0.75	High Extent	2.42	1.19	Low Extent		
2	Quality assurance lecturers are exempted from punishment.	1.82	0.93	Low Extent	1.92	0.95	Low Extent		
3	All defaulting lecturers are subject to punishment.	3.18	0.71	High Extent	2.67	1.03	High Extent		
4	Some lecturers are above quality assurance order.	1.64	1.64	Low Extent	2.00	1.00	Low Extent		
5	Quality assurance unit is not a respecter of any person when it comes to punishment.	2.64	1.22	High Extent	2.33	1.18	Low Extent		
Total Mean / SD		12.01	5.25		11.34	5.35			
Grand Mean /SD		2.40	1.05		2.27	1.07			

Source: Field Survey, 2022

The analysis in table 3 shows that only four mean responses are up to acceptance region of 2.50 this implies that; all lecturers are subject to quality assurance order, all defaulting lecturers are subject to punishment and quality assurance unit is not a respecter of any person when it comes to punishment

Hypotheses

Hypotheses 1: There is no significance difference in the mean responses of Male and Female Lecturers on the use of quality assurance to sustain Business Education Programme through effective Monitoring in Rivers State University.

Table 4: t-test Analysis on the mean responses of Male and Female Lecturers on the use of quality assurance to sustain Business Education programme through effective monitoring

Schools	n	x	sd	df	t.cal.	t.crit.	Lev	Decision
Female Lecturers	11	2.58	1.09		0.75	1.960	<u>Sign</u> 0.05	
Male Lecturers	12	2.25	0.97	21				Accepted

Source: Field Survey, 2024

The analysis in table 4 shows that the t-cal is less than the t-critical (t-cal < t-crit). Hence, the hypotheses was accepted. Therefore, there is no significant difference in the responses of male and female lecturers on the use of

quality assurance to sustain Business Education programme through effective monitoring in Rivers State University.

Hypotheses 2: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of Male and Female Lecturers on the use of quality assurance to sustain Business Education Programme through effective provision of intellectual learning materials in Rivers State University.

Table 5: t-test Analysis on the mean responses of Male and Female Lecturers on the use of Male and Female Lecturers on the use of quality assurance to sustain Business Education Programme through effective provision of intellectual learning materials.

Schools	n	x	sd	df	t.cal.	t.crit.	Lev	Decision
Female	11	2.36	0.91	21	0.58	1.960	0.05	Lecturers Accepted
Male Lecturers	12	2.13	0.96					

Source: Field Survey, 2024

The analysis in table 5 indicates that the t-cal is less than the t-critical ($t\text{-cal} < t\text{-crit}$). Hence, the hypotheses was accepted. Therefore, there is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female lectures on the use of quality assurance to sustain Business Education Programme through effective provision of intellectual learning material in Rivers State University.

Hypotheses 3: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of Male and Female Lecturers on the use of quality assurance to sustain disciplinary measure among Business Education Lecturers in Rivers State University.

Table 6 t-test Analysis on the mean responses of Male and Female Lecturers on the use of quality assurance to sustain disciplinary measure among Business Education Lecturers

Schools	n	x	sd	df	t.cal.	t.crit.	LevelofSign	Decision
Female Lecturers	11	2.40	1.05	21	0.29	1.960	0.05	Accepted
Male Lecturers	12	2.27	1.07					

Source: Field Survey, 2024

The analysis in table 6 indicates that the t-cal is less than the t-critical ($t\text{-cal} < t\text{-crit}$). Hence, the hypotheses was accepted. Therefore, there is no significant difference in the mean responses of Male and Female Lecturers on the use of quality assurance to sustain disciplinary Measure among Business Education Lecturers in Rivers State University.

Discussion of Findings

The discussion in this was highlighted according to the findings in the study.

On the Extent Quality Assurance can be used to sustain Business Education Programme through Effective Monitoring

The findings in table 1 revealed that quality assurance in Business Education programme ensures quality of personnel and provides guidelines for lecturers in the programme. This finding is in line with the view of Dill (2012) that the focus of accreditation through quality assurance is a comprehensive examining of the mission, resources and procedures in a programme

On the Extent Quality Assurance can be used to sustain Business Education Programme through effective provision of intellectual Learning Materials.

The findings in table 2 shows that quality assurance ensures that all Business Education students pass through SIWES training and also organize workshop for lecturers. This finding is in line with the view of Okon (2016) that quality assurance ensures strict compliance to training and re-training.

On the extent how Quality Assurance can be used to maintain Disciplinary Measure among Business Education Lecturers

The findings in table 3 indicates that all lecturers are subject to quality assurance order and all defaulting lecturers are subject to punishment. This is in line with the view of Oni (2015) that quality assurance ensures that every individual in a particular programme complies to lay down rules, regulations and guidelines. Regulations

Conclusion

Based on the discussion of findings of the study, it is evidenced that Quality assurance unit plays significant roles in Business Education Programme. It monitors the quality of the personnel involved in the programme, provides guidelines for programme, and employs disciplinary measures on defaulting lecturers or resource persons in a particular programme.

Recommendation

Based on the findings in the study, it was recommended that;

1. More emphasis should be placed on the quality of personnel in Business Education programme and the materials used through quality assurance.
2. Study materials resources and other gadgets that will promote should be provided through quality assurance. Unit
3. More disciplinary measures should be adopted by those in-charge of quality assurance on any individual that default

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